

New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Epirus, Greece

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1169150>

LECH BOROWIEC¹, SEBASTIAN SALATA²

^{1,2}Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław,
Przybyszewskiego 65, 51-148 Wrocław, Poland

e-mail: ¹ lech.borowiec@uwr.edu.pl, ² sdsalata@gmail.com

ABSTRACT. New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Epirus, Greece.

Seventy seven species of ants have been collected in Epirus (Northwestern Greece) in 2016, *Messor cf. clivorum* is new to Greece, 46 species are recorded from this region for the first time. At the moment 89 morphospecies are known from Epirus, 18 are identified only to complexes of cryptic taxa and their species status will be determined after future revisions.

KEY WORDS: ants, faunistics, Greece, Epirus, new regional records.

INTRODUCTION

Ant fauna of Greece is probably the richest in Europe, with about 280 species recorded within approximately 20 are endemic to this country (BOROWIEC 2014). Most of the recently collected material preserved in Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław, especially from the taxonomically difficult genera as *Temnothorax* MAYR, 1861 and *Tetramorium* MAYR, 1855, remained unidentified and it is estimated that at least 320 species occur in the Greek fauna, several of them new to science (BOROWIEC & SALATA, unpublished data). The first comprehensive checklist, comprising the past studies on Greek ants, was done recently by LEGAKIS (2011). In the last few years, the ant fauna of Greece was more intensively studied, as part of the inventory of the ants of the Mediterranean region (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016, BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, 2014a, 2014b, 2017a, 2017b, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2015a, 2015b, 2015c, 2016, 2017). As a result of those studies and including some unpublished data, Macedonia, with at least 158 species recorded, has the richest ant fauna among the geographic regions of Greece, followed by Thrace (116), Dodecanese (111), Ionian Islands (107), Aegean Islands (106), Peloponnese (102), Crete (98), Sterea Ellas (89), Thessaly (67), and Cyclades (46). At this moment Epirus, with published records for 43 species has the least known ant fauna. The only paper, demonstrating a greater number of species from Epirus noted 33 species collected in Zagori county (LEGAKIS 1983). Records of other 11 species were spread in various notes regarding Greek fauna (LEGAKIS 2011, WAGNER *et al.* 2017).

Epirus is a geographic and administrative region of Greece in the north-western part of the country with an area of 9 203 km². It is dominated by mountain ranges, with a narrow area of a Mediterranean habitats along the Ionian Sea. For such a large and diverse area, we can expect up to 110-120 ant species, given the diversity of neighboring

regions. In August and September 2016 we explored western part of the region and collected ants from 35 localities. As a result we present a list of collected ants, and a check-list of all ant species recorded so far in Epirus with comments on the taxonomy and distribution of poorly known or unnamed species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. On the banks of roads and forest ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella. On the rocks, the ants' nests were searched in rock crevices and using a chisel they tried to obtain a full nest sample. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% ethanol. Images of ant specimens were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1500 and Nikon SMZ 18 stereomicroscopes, Nikon D5200 photo camera and Helicon Focus software. Taxa in list of collected species are arranged alphabetically. General distribution is defined after BOROWIEC (2014) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA) preserved at the University of Wrocław. Geographical coordinates are given in decimal degrees N/E. The locality codes refer to the position in the coding system used in the DCGA preserved at the University of Wrocław. Localities are arranged chronologically. Material is deposited in the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

1. EPI-368 – Kanali, 39.06377/ 20.69971, 30 m, 26.08.2016, urban area;
2. EPI-369 – 700 m E of Kanali, 39.0638/ 20.70621, 50 m, 27.08.2016, oak forest;
3. EPI-370A – n. Kanali, 39.05458/ 20.70207, 15 m, 28.08.2016, oak forest;
4. EPI-370B – n. Kanali, 39.05388/ 20.70118, 20 m, 28.08.2016, pine forest;
5. EPI-371 – n. Profitis Ilias, 39.14414/ 20.67791, 495 m, 29.08.2016, pine forest;
6. EPI-372 – 1.7 km N K. Myrsini, 39.15021/ 20.63868, 148 m, 29.08.2016, roadsides in deciduous forest;
7. EPI-373 – n. K. Kotsanopoulo, 39.19554/ 20.72153, 95 m, 30.08.2016, stream valley with *Platanus* forest;
8. EPI-374 – 1.2 km NW of n. A. Kotsanopoulo, 39.23467/ 20.70309, 170 m, 30.08.2016, stream valley with *Platanus* forest;
9. EPI-375 – 2.3 km S of Sikies, 39.27264/ 20.6813, 215 m, 30.08.2016, stream valley with oak forest;
10. EPI-376 – Acheron Gorge, 39.28772/ 20.68153, 190 m, 30.08.2016, oak forest;
11. EPI-377 – 1.2 km S of Paleochori, 39.33311/ 20.71333, 270 m, 30.08.2016, oak forest;
12. EPI-382 – n. Vourgareli, 39.37527/ 21.19403, 795 m, 1.09.2016, coniferous forest;
13. EPI-383 – 2.4 km SE Pachtouri, 39.45672/ 21.27687, 655 m, 1.09.2016, deciduous forest;

14. EPI-384 – 1.2 km W Kapsala, 39.38274/ 21.24446, 770 m, 1.09.2016, coniferous forest;
15. EPI-385 – 1.3 km NE Athamania, 39.37919/ 21.23158, 850 m, 1.09.2016, coniferous forest;
16. EPI-390 – Assos, 39.34366/ 20.76352, 440 m, 3.09.2016, oak forest;
17. EPI-391 – Derviziana, 39.40497/ 20.78417, 510 m, 3.09.2016, deciduous forest;
18. EPI-392 – 2 km W Vargiades, 39.46044/ 20.78932, 900 m, 3.09.2016, oak forest;
19. EPI-393 – n. Analipsi, 39.47045/ 20.76412, 780 m, 3.09.2016, oak forest;
20. EPI-394 – n. Lippa, 39.46813/ 20.75004, 730 m, 3.09.2016, *Platanus* forest;
21. EPI-397 – Chrisopigi, 39.11252/ 21.20878, 580 m, 4.09.2016, stream valley with *Platanus* forest;
22. EPI-398 – n. Petra Kidiou, 39.13167/ 21.26109, 815 m, 4.09.2016, *Platanus* forest;
23. EPI-399 – n. Giannioti loc. 1, 39.1464/ 21.26745, 950 m, 4.09.2016, fir forest;
24. EPI-400 – n. Giannioti loc. 2, 39.14579/ 21.2725, 945 m, 5.09.2016, coniferous forest;
25. EPI-401 – Giannioti, 39.14318/ 21.27782, 945 m, 5.09.2016, mountain pasture;
26. EPI-402 – N of Giannioti, 39.15098/ 21.27466, 920 m, 5.09.2016, coniferous forest;
27. EPI-403 – 2 km S Skoulikaria, 39.158/ 21.27393, 890 m, 5.09.2016, oak forest;
28. EPI-404 – 1.5 km SE Karpino, 39.20065/ 21.26353, 950 m, 5.09.2016, pastures with mixed forest;
29. EPI-405 – n. Asfakero, 39.23388/ 21.23359, 790 m, 5.09.2016, oak forest;
30. EPI-406 – 1.9 km NE of Kanali, 39.06969/ 20.71734, 115 m, 6.09.2016, roadsides in oak forest;
31. EPI-407 – n. Polineri, 39.40835/ 20.32064, 230 m, 7.09.2016, olive plantation;
32. EPI-408 – 1.7 km SE of Polineri, 39.38802/ 20.33294, 355 m, 7.09.2016, oak forest;
33. EPI-409 – Ammoudia, 39.2446/ 20.48102, 1 m, 7.09.2016, sands near marshes;
34. EPI-410 – Kanallaki, 39.22716/ 20.62063, 110 m, 7.09.2016, stream valley with deciduous forest;
35. EPI-411 – n. Megadendro, 39.12726/ 20.62408, 270 m, 7.09.2016, deciduous forest.

LIST OF COLLECTED SPECIES

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 18, 25, 28, 30, 31, 32, 34, 35.

Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, especially its northern and western part. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983) under name *Aphaenogaster simonelli balcanica* EMERY, 1898.

2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Locality: 16.

Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Italy, Turkey and Israel. New to Epirus.

3. *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* WOLF, 1915

Localities: 13, 21.

Distribution: Western part of Balkan Peninsula and NE Italy. From Epirus recorded by WOLF (1915) and LEGAKIS (1983) under name *Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY, 1898).

4. *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*

Localities: 2, 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24, 27, 30.

Note: *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE) was recorded from almost whole southern Europe and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. Recent studies suggest that it is a group of cryptic species with at least 7 morphospecies occurring in Greece (BOROWIEC & SALATA, unpublished data), two of them were found in samples from Epirus. Their proper identification will be possible after the revision of the whole species complex. So far, at least one species was recorded from Epirus under name *A. subterranea* (LEGAKIS 1983).

5. *Bothriomyrmex communistus* SANTSCHI, 1919

Locality: 13.

Distribution: Western part of Mediterranean part of Europe and southern part of Central Europe north to Czech Republic and Slovakia. From Epirus recorded by SEIFERT (2012).

6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 5, 14, 18.

Distribution: Wide-spread in South Europe, southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983) under name *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798) and its synonymical name *Camponotus marginatus* (LATREILLE, 1798) but with a great probability the records of *C. marginatus* concern another species, *C. oertzeni* (see comments in the paragraph Doubtful published records).

7. *Camponotus atricolor* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Locality: 11.

Distribution: Austria, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Macedonia, Greece and Turkey (European part). New to Epirus.

8. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 10, 11, 13, 17, 32, 34.

Distribution: Italy, Balkan Peninsula, Turkey and the Near East. New to Epirus.

9. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 29.

Distribution: Almost whole Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. New to Epirus.

10. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Locality: 34.

Distribution: Balkan Peninsula and Turkey. New to Epirus.

11. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 19, 32.

Distribution: South Europe, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. New to Epirus.

12. ***Camponotus ligniperda*** (LATREILLE, 1802)
Locality: 15.
Distribution: Europe and Turkey, in Mediterranean countries in mountains only. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
13. ***Camponotus oertzeni*** FOREL, 1889
Localities: 11, 15, 16, 25, 26, 28.
Distribution: Greece, Serbia, Iran and Turkey, often misidentified with *C. aethiops*. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (2011).
14. ***Camponotus piceus*** (LEACH, 1825)
Localities: 2, 9, 15, 17, 25, 26, 29.
Distribution: South Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
15. ***Camponotus* cf. *piceus***
Locality: 18.
Note: Undescribed species noted by SEIFERT (2007) as *C. piceus* sp. 2. Known from Croatia and Greece. New to Epirus.
16. ***Camponotus vagus*** (SCOPOLI, 1763)
Localities: 1, 2, 12, 28, 33.
Distribution: Europe, Algeria, Georgia and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
17. ***Cataglyphis nodus*** (BRULLÉ, 1833)
Localities: 2, 3, 8, 9, 11, 12, 30, 33, 35.
Distribution: SE Europe, Transcaucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
18. ***Colobospis truncata*** (SPINOLA, 1808)
Localities: 2, 3.
Distribution: Europe, northern Africa, Transcaucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East.
New to Epirus.
19. ***Chalepoxenus muellerianus*** (FINZI, 1922)
Locality: 14.
Distribution: Social parasite of some *Temnothorax* species known from southern Europe and Turkey. New to Epirus.
20. ***Crematogaster schmidti*** (MAYR, 1853)
Localities: 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 16, 17, 18, 20, 26, 27, 29, 30, 32, 34, 35.
Distribution: SE Europe, Transcaucasian countries, Turkey and Iran. Not cited in the literature from Epirus but probably most or all records of *Crematogaster scutellaris ionia* in LEGAKIS (1983) concern *C. schmidti* (see comments in the paragraph Doubtful published records). True *C. ionia* FOREL, 1911 is xerothermophile species, common in Mediterranean habitats in Greece.
21. ***Crematogaster sordidula*** (NYLANDER, 1849)
Localities: 9, 11.
Distribution: NE Africa, Mediterranean part of Europe and western Turkey. New to Epirus.

22. *Dolichoderes quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)
Localities: 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 16, 17.
Distribution: Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
23. *Formica clara* FOREL, 1886
Locality: 1.
Distribution: Europe, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. New to Epirus.
24. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798
Locality: 28.
Distribution: Europe, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
25. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758
Localities: 13, 14, 15, 24, 26, 27.
Distribution: Europe, NW Africa, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
26. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798
Localities: 12, 20, 21.
Distribution: South Europe and southern parts of Central Europe and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).
27. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)
Localities: 8, 33.
Distribution: Mediterranean region, spread around the world as a tramp species. New to Epirus.
28. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
Localities: 1, 12, 15, 24, 27, 29.
Distribution: Europe, NW Africa, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (2011).
29. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016
Localities: 13, 14, 27, 28.
Distribution: Recently described species. Known from Austria, Hungary, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Greece and Turkey. New to Epirus.
30. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
Localities: 18, 26.
Distribution: Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. New to Epirus.
31. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER, 1792)
Localities: 12, 26.
Distribution: Europe, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983) but probably part of his records concern *Lasius illyricus*.
32. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
Localities: 15, 23, 24, 26, 28.
Distribution: Europe, NW Africa, Caucasian countries, Iran and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

33. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 7, 8.

Distribution: Croatia, Greece and Ukraine. New to Epirus.

34. *Lasius* cf. *illyricus*

Localities: 8, 24, 27.

Note: This morphospecies differs from typical *L. illyricus* in darker body colouration, distinctly smaller size and sparser setae on hind tibiae. Ants were collected only in very shadow habitats, close to mountain streams while typical *L. illyricus* prefers dry, open deciduous forests. Status of this form needs verification based on molecular studies. New to Epirus.

35. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)

Localities: 2, 3, 10, 19.

Distribution: Mediterranean part of Europe, Transcaucasian countries and Turkey. New to Epirus.

36. *Lasius mixtus* (NYLANDER, 1846)

Locality: 26.

Distribution: Europe and Caucasian countries. New to Epirus.

37. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHE, 1921

Localities: 23, 28.

Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Georgia, Iran and Turkey. New to Epirus.

38. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)

Locality: 1.

Distribution: NW Africa, Eastern part of Mediterranean Basin and Transcaucasian countries. New to Epirus.

39. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)

Localities: 7, 11, 27.

Distribution: Southern Europe from Italy to Turkey, eastern part of Central Europe, Caucasian countries, Israel, Iran. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

40. *Messor* cf. *clivorum*

Localities: 25, 27, 28.

Note: This morphospecies belongs to *M. structor* group and is well characterized by very long and flattened first segment of antennal funicle. This group of taxa needs revision where several infraspecific names of doubtful status were proposed. New to Greece and Epirus.

41. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Locality: 8.

Distribution: Recorded only from Greece and Turkish Thrace but probably most records of *M. capitatus* from eastern parts of Balkan Peninsula concern *M. hellenius*. New to Epirus.42. *Messor* cf. *semirufus*

Locality: 33.

Note: It is a member of *Messor semirufus* complex which comprises numerous names of various rank, partly available to nomenclature. Most taxa were described from the eastern

part of the Mediterranean Basin (BOROWIEC 2014, TOHMÉ & TOHMÉ 1981). Our material from Greece suggests the occurrence of at least three morphospecies of this complex in Greece. Their correct identification will be possible only after the revision of all names proposed in this group. Sample from Epirus belongs to the same morphospecies which was recorded by BRAČKO *et al.* (2016) from Thrace as *Messor cf. semirufus*. New to Epirus.

43. ***Messor cf. structor***

Localities: 11, 15, 18, 21, 35.

Note: According to the molecular studies, taxon previously named as a *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798) comprises two cryptic species, both can be found in different parts of the Balkan Peninsula (SCHLICK-STEINER *et al.* 2006). Since many available names of various rank were proposed in the *Messor structor* group, the proper identification of our samples is impossible prior to the revision of this group. New to Epirus.

44. ***Messor wasmanni*** KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 1, 2, 7, 29, 30, 32, 34, 35.

Distribution: Eastern part of Mediterranean Basin. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983) under synonymic name *Messor rufitarsis*.

45. ***Monomorium monomorium*** BOLTON, 1987

Locality: 1.

Distribution: NE Africa, South Europe, Turkey and Syria. New to Epirus.

46. ***Myrmecina graminicola*** (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 2, 26, 27.

Distribution: NE Africa, South and Central Europe, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. New to Epirus.

47. ***Myrmoxenus ravouxi*** (ANDRÉ, 1896)

Locality: 24.

Distribution: Social parasite of various *Temnothorax* species, known from Central and South Europe and Turkey. New to Epirus.

48. ***Pheidole cf. pallidula***

Localities: 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, 25, 28, 29, 31, 32, 34, 35.

Note: Mediterranean populations of taxa named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have been revised recently and classified into four distinct species (SEIFERT 2016). Three of them were recorded from Greece. Because the methodology used by SEIFERT (2016) to discriminate of “new taxa” is hard to verify, their status is under discussion. Former taxon “*P. pallidula*” was wide spread in Mediterranean area and was recorded from Epirus by LEGAKIS (1983). According to SEIFERT (2016) *P. balcanica* SEIFERT, 2016 probably occurs in this region.

49. ***Plagiolepis pallescens*** sensu RADCHENKO

Locality: 33.

Distribution and note: The status and nomenclature of taxon named by RADCHENKO (1996) as *Plagiolepis pallescens* was discussed in detail by BRAČKO *et al.* (2016). *Plagiolepis pallescens* sensu lato was recorded from eastern part of Mediterranean Basin. Revised localities of true *Plagiolepis pallescens* sensu RADCHENKO are in Greece, Caucasian countries and the Near East. New to Epirus.

50. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 1, 2, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 32, 34.

Distribution: Wide-spread in South Europe and southern parts of Central Europe, recorded also from NE Africa, Middle East, Caucasus and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

51. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE, 1936

Locality: 14.

Distribution: Social parasite of other *Plagiolepis* species known from South Europe, southern parts of Central Europe and Turkey. New to Epirus.

52. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 11, 19, 20, 25, 27, 29.

Distribution: Wide-spread in Europe, NW Africa, Caucasian countries, Turkey and the Near East. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

53. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 17, 20, 21, 26, 27, 28.

Distribution: SE Europe, Georgia and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

54. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 1

Localities: 5, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 16, 18, 28, 34.

Note: The status of most European species of genus *Solenopsis* requires an extensive revision.

GALKOWSKI *et al.* (2010) redescribed *Solenopsis fugax* and suggested that four distinct species groups occur in the territory of Europe and the Mediterranean area and that several taxa proposed by BERNARD (1950) are probably synonyms, but they did not take any formal nomenclatorial decisions. In Epirus, we found samples belonging to at least two distinct morphospecies of *S. lusitanica* complex. LEGAKIS (1983) recorded from Epirus *Solenopsis* sp. and suggested its relationships with *S. orbula* EMERY, 1875. However, short description noted in his paper placed his sample rather to *S. lusitanica* complex. New to Epirus.

55. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 2

Locality: 13.

Note: see note to *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 1. New to Epirus.

56. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859

Locality: 8.

Distribution: Morocco and eastern part of Mediterranean area from Italy to Turkey. New to Epirus.

57. *Tapinoma erraticum* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 1, 7, 8, 11, 13, 28.

Distribution: Wide-spread in Central and South Europe, Caucasian countries and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by LEGAKIS (1983).

58. *Temnothorax* cf. *albipennis*

Locality: 22.

Note: Greek species of *Temnothorax unifasciatus/tuberculatum* complex require revision.

Populations from Greece slightly differ from populations from Central Europe and perhaps represent other cryptic species. New to Epirus.

59. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)
Localities: 2, 4, 10.
Distribution: SE Europe and Turkey. New to Epirus.
60. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV, 1926)
Locality: 27.
Distribution: Europe, in Greece in its western part. Recorded from Epirus by LEGAKIS (1983) under name *Leptothorax nylanderi* and by SEIFERT & CSÖSZ (2015).
61. *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY, 1869)
Localities: 18, 34.
Distribution: Mediterranean part of Europe and Turkey. New to Epirus.
62. *Temnothorax* cf. *interruptus*
Locality: 34.
Note: This is a new species known from Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece and Turkey. Its description will be published in a revision of *Temnothorax interruptus* complex (Csösz *et al.* in print). New to Epirus.
63. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)
Localities: 5, 9, 10, 11, 32.
Distribution: South Europe north to Austria and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by Csösz *et al.* (2014a).
64. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)
Localities: 8, 13, 16, 17, 19, 20, 23, 24, 26, 29, 32.
Distribution: Central and South Europe, Caucasian countries, Iran and Turkey. New to Epirus.
65. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)
Localities: 14, 29.
Distribution: NE Africa, Mediterranean part of Europe, Turkey and Israel. New to Epirus.
66. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869
Localities: 1, 2, 5, 32, 34.
Distribution: Croatia, Greece and Montenegro. New to Epirus.
67. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)
Locality: 14.
Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Turkey and the Near East. New to Epirus.
68. *Temnothorax* cf. *tauricus*
Localities: 2, 3, 4.
Note: This is an arboricolous species, in Greece collected only from Ionian Islands and coastal part of Epirus. This is the same species recorded by BRAČKO *et al.* (2014) from Montenegro as *Temnothorax* sp. 1 (BRAČKO pers. inf.). It belongs to *T. unifasciatus* complex. It is similar to *Temnothorax tauricus* (RUZSKY, 1902) known from Armenia, Bulgaria, Ukraine and Caucasus, but differs in several details. Its status will be clarified after the revision of all Greek species of *T. unifasciatus* complex. New to Epirus.

69. *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*

Locality: 27.

Note: Greek species of *Temnothorax unifasciatus/tuberum* complex requires revision. Morphospecies from locality 27 is similar to *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934), known from Austria, Greek Macedonia and Turkey. New to Epirus.

70. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI, 1928)

Localities: 23, 25.

Distribution: Central Europe and Balkan Peninsula. New to Epirus.

71. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*

Localities: 12, 13, 18, 28.

Note: Greek species of *Temnothorax unifasciatus/tuberum* complex requires revision. Populations from Greece slightly differ from populations from Central Europe and perhaps represent other cryptic species. New to Epirus.

72. *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus*

Locality: 24.

Note: Greek species of *Temnothorax unifasciatus/tuberum* complex requires revision. Populations from Greece slightly differ from populations from Central Europe and perhaps represent other cryptic species. Recorded from Epirus by LEGAKIS (1983) under name *Temnothorax unifasciatus*.

73. *Tetramorium* cf. *caespitum*

Localities: 1, 7, 13, 14, 26.

Note: According to WAGNER *et al.* (2017), ten distinct species of *T. cf. caespitum* complex occur in Europe. At least one species of this complex was recorded from Epirus by LEGAKIS (1983). WAGNER *et al.* (2017) recorded from Epirus *Tetramorium breviscapus* WAGNER, ARTHOFER, SEIFERT, MUSTER, STEINER & SCHLICK-STEINER, 2017, newly described from Croatia, Bosnia and Hercegovina and Pindos Mountains in Epirus but our samples without doubts belong to *T. caespitum* or *T. impurum*. Both species to proper identification need nest samples with males but we have only workers.

74. *Tetramorium diomedeam* EMERY, 1908

Localities: 32, 33.

Distribution: Balkan Peninsula and Turkey. New to Epirus.

75. *Tetramorium* cf. *flavidulum*

Locality: 33.

Note: In the eastern part of Mediterranean Basin, *Tetramorium flavidulum* group is represented by several morphospecies with centre of diversity in Anatolian Turkey (our unpublished data). Material from Greece suggests the occurrence of at least three distinct species in this country. Proper identification of the sample from Epirus is impossible prior to the revision of all taxa of *T. flaviulum* group. New to Epirus.

76. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Locality: 11.

Distribution: Recently described species known only from Croatia and Greece, but probably many records of *Tetramorium semilaeve* from Balkan countries concern *T. kephalosi*. From Epirus recorded by SALATA & BOROWIEC (2017).

77. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

Localities: 14, 33.

Distribution: South Europe and southern parts of Central Europe and Turkey. From Epirus recorded by Csósz *et al.* (2007).

DOUBTFUL PUBLISHED RECORDS

***Aphaenogaster festae* EMERY, 1915**

LEGAKIS (2011) recorded this species from Epirus based on unpublished checklist of ants of Greece prepared by C.A. COLLINGWOOD. This taxon is distributed only in eastern Greece, from Thrace to Dodecanese, and LEGAKIS (2011) record probably concerns a similar species *A. muelleriana* WOLF, 1915.

***Aphaenogaster ionia* SANTSCHI, 1933**

LEGAKIS (2011) recorded from Epirus both *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898) and *Aphaenogaster ionia* SANTSCHI, 1933. According to the recent revision of European species of *A. testaceopilopsa* group (BOER 2013), both names are synonymous.

***Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY, 1898)**

A. ovaticeps was recorded from Epirus by WOLF (1915) and LEGAKIS (1983). Our material of the species of *A. ovaticeps* complex and study of *A. ovaticeps* type specimen show that the complex comprises three species, partly separated geographically: true *A. ovaticeps* from northern Italy, *A. muelleriana* from Northeastern Italy, Ionian Islands and Adriatic coast from Croatia to southern Epirus, and an undescribed taxon from western Sterea Ellas and western and southern Peloponnese, wrongly identified as *A. splendida* by BOROWIEC & SALATA (2013). Therefore the records of WOLF (1915) and LEGAKIS (1983) certainly concern *A. muelleriana*.

***Camponotus marginatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)**

LEGAKIS (1983) recorded this taxon from Aaos river near Konitsa, but the name is recently treated as synonym of *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798). With great probability LEGAKIS (1983) record concerns a similar species *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889 which was frequently reported from SE Europe under name *C. marginatus*.

***Crematogaster scutellaris ionia* FOREL, 1911**

LEGAKIS (1983) recorded this taxon from four localities in Zagori area and noted that it is very common species there. According to our material, only *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR, 1853) occurs in Epirus, where it is one of the commonest arboricolous ants. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL, 1911, however, is more common in mediterranean habitats of central and southern Greece. Its presence in Epirus is possible in coastal part of the region, while in mountains of Zagori its presence is doubtful, therefore the records by LEGAKIS (1983) most probably concern *C. schmidti*. Taxa of *C. schmidti/ionia* group need revision based on molecular studies. Our material from Balkan Peninsula and Aegean Turkey suggests that it is complex of several cryptic species.

***Lasius niger* (LINNAEUS, 1758)**

LEGAKIS (2011) recorded this species from Epirus but only known relevant old references indicate occurrence of this species in this part of Balkan Peninsula only from Republic of Macedonia and Greek Western Macedonia Region, near the border with Epirus. *Lasius niger* complex, after revision by SEIFERT (1992), comprise several species, partly described recently. Thus all records before this revision are unreliable and need confirmation. True *Lasius niger* (LINNAEUS, 1758) is very rare in Greece (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012).

***Leptothorax nylanderi* (FÖRSTER, 1850)**

LEGAKIS (1983) recorded this species from Vrissohori and Kapesovo. Recent revision of *Temnothorax nylanderi* group by Csösz *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that populations from northwestern Greece belong to *T. crassispinus* (KARAVAEV, 1926) while true *T. nylanderi* is more western species, with no certain records from Greece.

***Messor rufitarsis* (FABRICIUS, 1804)**

LEGAKIS (1983) recorded this species from 10 localities in Epirus and noted that it is very common species. He probably misinterpreted this taxon with *Messor rufitarsis* FÖRSTER, 1850, now synonym of *Messor barbarus* (LINNAEUS, 1767), while *Messor rufitarsis* (FABRICIUS, 1804) is now synonym of *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798). *Messor barbarus* was recorded as common species from several countries of Balkan Peninsula but now populations from this region are treated as independent taxon *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910 while true *M. barbarus* occurs only in the western part of Mediterranean basin. Both *M. wasmanni* and *M. structor* sensu lato (see note above under *Messor* cf. *structor*) occur in Epirus but only the first species is common in this area. *Messor structor* has cryptic life and appears rare. We conclude that LEGAKIS (1983) records of *Messor rufitarsis* (Fabricius, 1804) from Epirus concern *Messor wasmanni*.

***Proformica nitida* KUZNETSOV-UGAMSKY, 1923**

LEGAKIS (2011) recorded this species from Epirus based on unpublished checklist of ants of Greece prepared by C. A. COLLINGWOOD. According to the revision of the genus *Proformica* by DLUSSKY (1969), this is Central Asiatic species, therefore its occurrence in Greece is doubtful and probably concerns some other species of the genus.

***Tetramorium semilaeve* ANDRÉ, 1889**

LEGAKIS (1983) recorded this species from Vissahora. Recent revisions of the *Tetramorium semilaeve* complex showed that true *T. semilaeve* is distributed only in western part of Mediterranean Basin (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2015, 2016, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017). In Greece occur at least two other species of this group: recently described *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017 and *T. hippocratis* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987. The second species is known only from Thrace, Dodecanese and Crete while *T. kephalosi* is widespread in Greece. LEGAKIS (1983) record concerns probably this taxon.

Checklist of ants of Epirus

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)
2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)
3. *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* WOLF, 1915
4. *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea*
5. *Bothriomyrmex communistus* SANTSCHI, 1919
6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)
7. *Camponotus atricolor* (NYLANDER, 1849)
8. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)
9. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)
10. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920
11. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

12. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)
13. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889
14. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)
15. *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*
16. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)
17. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)
18. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)
19. *Colobospis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)
20. *Crematogaster* cf. *ionia*
21. *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR, 1853)
22. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)
23. *Dolichoderes quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)
24. *Formica cinerea* MAYR, 1853
25. *Formica clara* FOREL, 1886
26. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798
27. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758
28. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798
29. *Formica lugubris* ZETTERSTEDT, 1838
30. *Formica rufibarbis* FABRICIUS, 1793
31. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)
32. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
33. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016
34. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
35. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER, 1792)
36. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
37. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935
38. *Lasius* cf. *illyricus*
39. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)
40. *Lasius mixtus* (NYLANDER, 1846)
41. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI, 1921
42. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
43. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)
44. *Messor* cf. *clivorum*
45. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
46. *Messor* cf. *semirufus*
47. *Messor* cf. *structor*

48. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910
49. *Monomorium monomorium* BOLTON, 1987
50. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)
51. *Myrmica ravasinii* FINZI, 1923
52. *Myrmica ruginodis* NYLANDER, 1846
53. *Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT, 1861
54. *Myrmoxenus ravouxi* (ANDRÉ, 1896)
55. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*
56. *Plagiolepis pallescens* sensu RADCHENKO
57. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)
58. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE, 1936
59. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)
60. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)
61. *Proceratium algiricum* FOREL, 1899
62. *Proformica* cf. *nasuta*
63. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 1
64. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica* sp. 2
65. *Stenammina striatulum* EMERY, 1895
66. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859
67. *Tapinoma erraticum* (LATREILLE, 1798)
68. *Temnothorax* cf. *albipennis*
69. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)
70. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAEV, 1926)
71. *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY, 1869)
72. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)
73. *Temnothorax* cf. *interruptus*
74. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)
75. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)
76. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869
77. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)
78. *Temnothorax* cf. *tauricus*
79. *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*
80. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI, 1928)
81. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*
82. *Temnothorax* cf. *unifasciatus*
83. *Tetramorium breviscapus* WAGNER, ARTHOFER, SEIFERT, MUSTER, STEINER & SCHLICK-STEINER, 2017

84. *Tetramorium cf. caespitum*
85. *Tetramorium diomedaeum* EMERY, 1908
86. *Tetramorium cf. flavidulum*
87. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
88. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017
89. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks to Dr. J. Świętojańska (University of Wrocław, Poland) for her assistance during field trips of the senior author.

REFERENCES

- BERNARD F. 1950 Notes sur les fourmis de France. II. Peuplement des montagnes meridionales. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France* 115: 1–36.
- BOER P. 2013. Revision of the European ants of the *Aphaenogaster testaceopilosa*-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie* 156: 57–93.
- BOROWIEC L. 2014. Catalogue of ants of Europe, the Mediterranean Basin and adjacent regions (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* (Special issue – Monograph) 25: 1–340.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2012. Ants of Greece – checklist, comments and new faunistic data (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 23: 461–563
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2013. Ants of Greece – additions and corrections (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 24: 335–401.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2014a. Redescription of *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, 1889, new status and notes on ants from Kefalonia, Greece (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* 25: 499–517.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2014b. Review of Mediterranean members of the *Aphaenogaster ceconii* group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), with description of four new species. *Zootaxa* 3861: 40–60.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2017a. New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Sterea Ellas, Greece. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 25(020): 1–3 [online].
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2017b. Ants of the Peloponnese, Greece (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Polish Journal of Entomology* 86: 193–235.
- BOROWIEC L., GALKOWSKI C., SALATA S. 2015. What is *Tetramorium semilaeve* ANDRÉ, 1883? (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmecinae). *ZooKeys* 512: 39–62.
- BOROWIEC L., GALKOWSKI C., SALATA S. 2016. Redescription of *Tetramorium atlante* CAGNIANT, 1970, new status (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmecinae). *Annales Zoologici* 66: 43–52.
- BRAČKO G., GOMBOC M., LUPŠE B., MARIĆ R., PRISTOVŠEK U. 2014. New faunistic data on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the southern part of Montenegro. *Natura Sloveniae* 16: 41–51.
- BRAČKO G., KIRAN K., KARAMAN C., SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2016. Survey of the ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the Greek Thrace. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 4: e7945.
- CSÓSZ S., MARKÓ B. 2004. Redescription of *Tetramorium hungaricum* RÖSZLER, 1935, a related species of *T. caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Myrmecologische Nachrichten* 6: 49–59.
- CSÓSZ S., HEINZE J., MIKÓ I. 2015. Taxonomic *Synopsis* of the Ponto-Mediterranean Ants of *Temnothorax nylanderii* Species-Group. PLOS ONE 10 (11): e0140000.
- CSÓSZ S., RADCHENKO A., SCHULZ A. 2007. Taxonomic revision of the Palaearctic *Tetramorium chefketi* species complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Zootaxa* 1405: 1–38.
- CSÓSZ S., SEIFERT B., MÜLLER B., TRINDL A., SCHULZ A., HEINZE J. 2014a. Cryptic diversity in the Mediterranean *Temnothorax lichtensteini* species complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 14: 75–88.

- CSŐSZ S., WAGNER H.C., BOZSÓ M., SEIFERT B., ARTHOFER W., SCHLICK-STEINER B.C., STEINER F.M., PÉNZES Z. 2014b. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927 stat. rev. is the proposed scientific name for *Tetramorium* sp. C sensu SCHLICK-STEINER *et al.* (2006) based on combined molecular and morphological evidence (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Zoologischer Anzeiger – A Journal of Comparative Zoology* 253(6): 469–481.
- DLUSSKY G.M. 1969. Ants of the genus *Proformica* RÜZS. of the USSR and contiguous countries (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 48: 218–232.
- GALKOWSKI C., CASEVITZ-WEULERSEE J., CAGNIANT H. 2010. Redescription de *Solenopsis fugax* (LATREILLE, 1798) et notes sur les *Solenopsis* de France (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Revue Française d'Entomologie* 32(3): 151–163.
- LEGAKIS A. 1983. First contribution to the study of the ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of the Zagori Region (Epirus, Greece): an annotated list of species. *Entomologia Hellenica* 1: 3–6.
- LEGAKIS A. 2011. Annotated list of the ants (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of Greece. *Hellenic Zoological Archives* 7: 1–55.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2015a. Redescription of *Crematogaster cypria* SANTSCHI, 1930, new status, with description of two new related species from Greece and Turkey (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *ZooKeys* 505: 59–77.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2015b. Redescription of *Temnothorax antigoni* (FOREL, 1911) and description of its new social parasite *Temnothorax curtisetosus* sp. n. from Turkey (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *ZooKeys* 523: 129–148.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2015c. A taxonomic revision of the genus *Oxyopomyrmex* ANDRÉ, 1881 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Zootaxa* 4025: 1–66.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2016. A new species of the *Aphaenogaster cecconii* group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Rhodes. *Zootaxa* 4170: 194–200.
- SALATA S., BOROWIEC L. 2017. Species of *Tetramorium semilaeve* complex from Balkans and western Turkey, with description of two new species of (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmicinae). *Annales Zoologici* 67: 279–313.
- SCHLICK-STEINER B.C., STEINER F.M., MODER K., SEIFERT B., SANETRA M., DYRESON E., STAUFFER C., CHRISTIAN E. 2006a. A multidisciplinary approach reveals cryptic diversity in Western Palearctic *Tetramorium* ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 40 (1): 259–273
- SCHLICK-STEINER B.C., STEINER F.M., KONRAD H., MARKO B., CSŐSZ S., HELLER G., FERENCZ B., SIPOS B., CHRISTIAN E., STAUFFER C. 2006b. More than one species of *Messor harvester* ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Central Europe. *European Journal of Entomology* 103: 469–476.
- SEIFERT B. 1992. A taxonomic revision of the Palearctic members of the ant subgenus *Lasius* s.str. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Abhandlungen und Berichte des Naturkundemuseums Görlitz* 66(5): 1–67.
- SEIFERT B. 2007. Die Ameisen Mittel- und Nordeuropas. Görlitz: Lutra Verlags- und Vertriebsgesellschaft, 368 pp.
- SEIFERT B. 2012. A review of the West Palearctic species of the ant genus *Bothriomyrmex* EMERY, 1869 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Myrmecological News* 17: 91–104.
- SEIFERT B. 2016. Inconvenient hyperdiversity – the traditional concept of “*Pheidole pallidula*” includes four cryptic species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Soil Organisms* 88: 1–17.
- SEIFERT B., CSŐSZ S. 2015. *Temnothorax crasecundus* sp. n. – a cryptic Eurocaucasian ant species (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) discovered by Nest Centroid Clustering. *ZooKeys* 479: 37–64.
- STEINER F.M., SEIFERT B., MODER K., SCHLICK-STEINER B.C. 2010. A multisource solution for a complex problem in biodiversity research: description of the cryptic ant species *Tetramorium alpestre* sp. n. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 249: 223–254.
- TOHMÉ G., TOHMÉ H. 1981. Les fourmis du genre *Messor* en Syrie. Position systématique. Description de quelques aîlés et de formes nouvelles. *Répartition géographique. Ecologia Mediterranea* 7(1): 139–153.
- WAGNER H.C., ARTHOFER W., SEIFERT B., MUSTER C., STEINER F.M. & SCHLICK-STEINER B.C. 2017. Light at the end of the tunnel: Integrative taxonomy delimits cryptic species in the *Tetramorium caespitum* complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Myrmecological News* 25: 95–129.
- WOLF K. 1915. Studien über palaearktische Formiciden. I. Bericht des Naturwissenschaftlich-Medizinischen Vereins in Innsbruck 35: 37–52.
- ZIMMERMANN S. 1935 [1934]. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Ameisenfauna Süddalmatiens. *Verhandlungen der Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien* 84: 1–65.

Figs 1–2. 1. *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* WOLF, worker; 2. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, major worker (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 1–2. 1. *Aphaenogaster muelleriana* WOLF, robotnica; 2. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, duża robotnica (skala = 1 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

Figs 3–4. 3. *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*, minor worker; 4. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, worker (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 3–4. 3. *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*, mała robotnica; 4. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, robotnica (skala = 1 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

Figs 5–6. 5. *Lasius mixtus* (NYLANDER), worker; 6. *Monomorium monorum* BOLTON, worker (scale bar for 5 = 1 mm, for 6 = 0.5 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 5–6. 5. *Lasius mixtus* (NYLANDER), robotnica; 6. *Monomorium monorum* BOLTON, robotnica (skala dla 5 = 1 mm, dla 6 = 0.5 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

Figs 7–8. 7. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, worker; 8. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ), worker (scale bar = 1 mm) (photo L. Borowiec).

Ryc. 7–8. 7. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, robotnica; 8. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ), robotnica (skala = 1 mm) (fot. L. Borowiec).

STRESZCZENIE

Nowe stwierdzenia mrówek (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) z prowincji Epirus, Grecja

W czasie badań faunistycznych mrówek prowincji Epirus (północno-zachodnia Grecja) złowiono 77 gatunków, 46 z nich nie było do tej pory podawanych z tej części Grecji. Obecnie lista gatunków znanych z Epirusu obejmuje 89 gatunków, 18 z nich jest zaklasyfikowanych tylko do kompleksów kryptycznych taksonów, których status gatunkowy będzie weryfikowany w przyszłych rewizjach. Przedyskutowano też 10 gatunków, które były podawane z prowincji Epirus, prawdopodobnie przez błędne oznaczenie lub błędą interpretację. Osiem interesujących gatunków zilustrowano na kolorowych fotografiach.

Accepted: 19 January 2018; published: 8 February 2018

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution License <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>